

INVESTIGATIONS ON EXPERIMENTAL FATIGUE LIFE AND DAMAGE OF DESIGNED HYBRID COMPOSITE LAMINATES WITH NEGATIVE AND POSITIVE POISSON'S RATIO

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Composite material design with negative Poisson's ratio may be employed in many specific industrial applications to increase the fatigue strength and improve resistance to failure. For this purpose, the authors designed an 8-layer hybrid laminate of carbon/glass/epoxy with negative Poisson's ratio of -0.161 and elastic modulus of 27.50 GPa. For comparison another laminate was made with only different angle of layers, but with positive Poisson's ratio of 0.156 and similar elastic modulus of about 27.78 GPa. The obtained mechanical properties from classical laminate theory and experiments are in excellent agreement. The fatigue strength of the laminate with negative Poisson's ratio is about 60% larger than that obtained for positive Poisson's ratio. The failure type of the laminate with negative Poisson's ratio is not catastrophic and behaves similar to pseudo-ductile fracture. More details of the experiments and results are discussed in this paper.

Keywords: Fatigue, negative Poisson's ratio, composite, hybrid, material design

INTRODUCTION

Composite laminates are commonly utilised in various industries due to their high strength-to-weight ratios and unique mechanical properties. These materials possess superior strength, stiffness, and durability compared to traditional materials, making them ideal for a variety of applications. However, it should be noted that the mechanical properties of composite laminates can vary depending on the specific design and composition of the material. Proper testing and evaluation are crucial to determine the suitability of a particular composite laminate for a given application [1,2]. One new type of composite material, which could provide advantages over routine composites, is auxetic composite materials, with negative Poisson's ratio. The Poisson's ratio is defined as the negative ratio of transverse strain to longitudinal strain in the direction of loading. From a physical standpoint, when an object is subjected to tensile force, it tends to contract in the direction perpendicular to the applied compressive force and expand under the influence of tensile force. In contrast to classic materials, auxetic materials display a reverse mechanism of deformation under stress. When subjected to tensile stress along their longitudinal axis, they may exhibit positive stress in the direction perpendicular to the loading axis. It is possible to create composite laminates with negative Poisson's ratio (auxetic) by changing the layers angles, matrix material, number of layers, hybrid fibres, and the volume fraction of matrix and fibre. Typical characteristics of these materials

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include enhancement in fracture toughness, increased strength and impact energy absorption [3]. Also, from classical theory of elasticity, many mechanical properties depend on the Poisson's ratio of the material. For example, the shear modulus of elasticity is increased when Poisson's ratio is decreased or become negative. Also, the Bulk modulus of elasticity is decreased by decreasing the Poisson's ratio.

Herakovich [4] used the theory of two-dimensional lamination to investigate changes in Poisson's ratio at different angles. In this study, a negative Poisson's ratio was observed for carbon/epoxy composite at certain angles. Theocaris et al. [5] developed a formulation to calculate the elastic modulus and Poisson's ratio in composite laminates, and investigated the effect of mesophase layer between the fibre and matrix on the elastic behaviour of composite materials. Zhang et al. [6] investigated the feasibility of manufacturing auxetic laminates and also studied the effect of the mechanical properties and angle of the layers on negative Poisson's ratio. Hsieh and Tuan [7] presented a numerical model to calculate the Poisson's ratio and compared it with composite laminate experimental results based on experimental data of fibre and matrix properties. Harkati et al. [8] investigated the effect of changing the type of fibre on the Poisson's ratio of auxetic laminates.

Accurate measurement of strain is also important for analysing the behaviour of composite structures under different loadings [9]. Extensometers and strain gauges are commonly used mechanical devices for measuring displacement and strain by connecting them to the specimen. However, they have limitations, such as high cost, and limited access to the full range of displacement and strain across the specimen surface. Although their output results may be acceptable, these limitations have prompted researchers to explore alternative methods for measuring displacement and strain [10-12]. The digital image correlation method (DIC) is an optical method that has the ability to accurately measure displacement and strain in different directions [13]. Hosseini-Toudeshky and Navaei [14] characterised the mechanical properties of the interphase between the fibre and matrix in single glass fibre epoxy specimens using precise displacement measurements with the DIC method. This method provides a qualitative full-field measurement of fibre orientation while maintaining high resolution. Therefore, in recent years, the use of digital image correlation (DIC) to measure the Poisson's ratio of composite materials has increased [15-19]. Mehrabian and Boukhili [20] used the DIC method to measure the axial strain distribution in bolted and hybrid bolted-bonded joints of woven carbon-epoxy composites.

Suwarta et al. [21] investigated the fatigue behaviour of pseudo-ductile unidirectional (UD) thin-ply hybrid laminates made of thin-ply glass/carbon/epoxy plies under two scenarios: without any initial damage (pristine hybrids) and after the introducing of damage in the laminates by loading past the pseudo-yield point (over loaded hybrids). Ben Ameer et al. [22] studied the mechanical behaviour of carbon/flax hybrid composites under static and fatigue tensile loading. The failure characteristics and parameters used in the fatigue tests were deduced from the static ones. The effect of the applied stress level, hybridisation and stacking sequences on the stiffness, hysteresis loops, dissipated energy and damping, were studied for various number of cycles during fatigue tests.

A combination of high strength carbon fibre layers with proper orientations and different resins could be used to design composites with negative Poisson's ratio. On the other hand, combining glass fibre layers with different angles and various resins usually lead to the design and production of laminates with positive Poisson's ratio. Hybrid composites could be an alternative for designing laminates with negative Poisson's ratio. They also do not deteriorate suddenly due to the difference between the mechanical properties of the fibres. Therefore, this research focusses on fatigue behavior of auxetic hybrid composites.

The aim of this research was to explore how Poisson's ratio affects the fatigue performance of hybrid composite laminates. For this purpose, two composite laminates with almost equal elastic modulus were designed but one with negative Poisson's ratio and the other one with positive Poisson's ratio. At first, static tensile tests were performed to obtain the stress-strain behaviours for both laminates. Then, fatigue tests were also performed for both type of laminates and the obtained results are discussed in this paper. Elastic modulus degradation of the laminates due to fatigue loading is also investigated.

EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAMME

To design the auxetic hybrid laminate, the classical laminate theory (CLT) was used to determine the proper stacking sequences, the fibres' arrangement, and their angles. In this research, the CLT formulations were implemented in a developed code in MATLAB software. The 8-layers laminates of [C/C/G/C]_s were considered for design of laminate with positive Poisson's ratio. Also, a laminate with negative Poisson's ratio was also designed with almost similar axial elastic modulus and hybrid composition of carbon and glass fibres but layers orientations.

[10/45/-45/90]_s lay-up with [C/C/G/C]_s arrangement were used to design laminate with positive Poisson's ratio ($\nu = +0.156$ and $E_{11} = 27.67$ GPa). The external angle of this laminate was chosen close to the loading axis. Table 1 also shows some examples of obtained laminates from classical laminate theory with negative Poisson's ratio and with similar elastic modulus as laminates with positive Poisson's ratio. Among these, the stacking sequence of [10/80/10/70]_s, was selected for manufacturing of specimens, because of the similarity of the absolute value of Poisson's ratio and its outer layer's angle with the laminate with positive Poisson's ratio.

TABLE 1 Obtained layups for laminates with negative Poisson's ratio from CLT

Stacking Sequence	Axial Elastic Modulus- E_{11} (GPa)	Poisson's Ratio
[10 _c /20 _c /30 _g /80 _c] _s	27.55	-0.1418
[10 _c /80 _c /10 _g /70 _c] _s	27.43	-0.16087
[20 _c /10 _c /90 _g /80 _c] _s	27.65	-0.11474
[30 _c /60 _c /20 _g /10 _c] _s	27.20	-0.17025
[60 _c /30 _c /20 _g /10 _c] _s	27.20	-0.17025
[80 _c /60 _c /10 _g /10 _c] _s	27.52	-0.12999

The experimental studies were conducted under static and fatigue loadings. Following the ASTM D3039 [23] and ASTM D3479 [24] standards, the hybrid specimens with two different stacking sequences with positive and negative Poisson's ratio were manufactured. Both laminates containing the arrangement of [C/C/G/C]_s layups with the same axial tensile elastic modulus (E_{11}). Figure 1 shows the geometry and dimensions of the specimens.

To analyse the fatigue strength, the lay-ups were subjected to loading with a magnitude of 75% of the ultimate tensile stress and a stress ratio of 0.1. Damage initiation and the lifespan of the specimens under these conditions were evaluated.

FIGURE 1 Geometry and dimensions of the specimens

The materials used to make these specimens were unidirectional carbon fibres weighing 300 gr.m^{-2} , unidirectional glass fibre weighing 400 gr.m^{-2} , and KER828 epoxy resin with Theta hardener and mixing ratio of 10%. The laminates were prepared using the hand layup method with a vacuum pressure of 0.8 bar and cured for one week at room temperature. To prevent damage at the edges of specimens, the water jet technique was used for cutting and sizing.

To prepare the specimens for DIC measurements, they were entirely painted white after manufacturing. After drying, black speckles were sprayed on their surfaces. During the tests, the painted surface of the specimens was captured by a high-quality digital camera (Canon 6d) from a short distance at a rate of 25 frames/s. This process enables the use of the DIC method with GOM software to analysis the variation of strains during the tests. See Figure 2 for more details of experimental procedure.

FIGURE 2 Manufacturing, testing and analysis procedure.
 a) laminates hand layup, b) sized specimens, c) painted specimens, d) test setup and cyclic loading, e) specimen at failure and f) DIC analysis

Static Tensile Experiment

To understand the stress behaviour of laminates, static tensile tests were conducted. These tests were performed using a DARTEC 9600 hydraulic machine. The specimens were subjected to pure tension at a $0.1 \text{ mm}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ speed until failure. During this time, the gauge displacement table and force applied to the specimen were recorded for every second. Based on this data and the cross-sectional area of the sample, the applied stress was calculated for each second. Additionally, DIC was employed to obtain the strain distribution from the beginning of the test until its failure.

To perform static tests, three specimens have been manufactured for each layup, and subsequently subjected to testing. Among these, the successful results for two tests were used, and their averages are reported as the final outcomes. The obtained stress-strain diagrams for both laminates are shown in Figure 3. This figure shows that both laminates with positive and negative Poisson's ratios have almost the same axial elastic modulus in the linear part of the curves. It is also clear that the ultimate tensile stress for the laminate with positive Poisson's ratio is larger than that with negative Poisson's ratio. Also, significant damage initiation stress (initiation of nonlinearity at stress-strain curves) for the specimen with positive Poisson's ratio is larger than that for negative Poisson's ratio. However, failure strain of the laminate with negative Poisson's ratio is larger than that of the specimen with positive Poisson's ratio. It is also worth to note that according to the visual observations and digital camera recording during experimental testing and analysis of the stress-strain curve, occurrence of damage and failure behaviour of the laminate with negative Poisson's ratio is more similar to pseudo-ductile composite materials. For more comparisons, the obtained quantities damage initiation and failure strain are depicted in Table 2 for both laminates. It is also more discussed in the results and discussion part of this paper.

FIGURE 3 Stress-strain behaviours of laminates with positive and negative Poisson's ratio

TABLE 2 Specimens mechanical properties

Laminate Type	Stacking Sequence	Axial Elastic Modulus- E_{11} (GPa)		UTS (MPa)	Damage Initiation Stress (MPa)	Fracture Strain (%)	Poisson's Ratio
		CLT	Exp.				
Negative Poisson's Ratio	$[10_c/80_c/10_g/70_c]_s$	27.43	27.50	136	115	1.13	-0.161
Positive Poisson's Ratio	$[10_c/45_c/-45_g/90_c]_s$	27.67	27.78	190	165	0.93	0.156

FIGURE 4 Final failure of hybrid specimens under static loading

Fatigue Experiment

Fatigue experiments were performed for both type of specimens with negative and positive Poisson's ratios. The type of fatigue loading was sinusoidal tension-tension waveform with the stress ratio (R) of 0.1 and frequency of 5 Hz. The magnitude of the maximum stress was selected to be 75% of the significant damage initiation stress (initiating nonlinearity in the stress-strain curves) of each laminate. It is worth to note that the maximum stress for fatigue testing of specimens with positive Poisson's ratio was 101.2 MPa and for specimen with negative Poisson's ratio was 86.2 MPa. A DARTEC 9600 hydraulic machine was also used for fatigue testing at room temperature. Fatigue tests were conducted until failure and the number of cycles were recorded, as depicted in Table 3. It

is worth to note that due to initial constraints and university funding limitations, the results of two successful fatigue tests were considered in the analyses. The history of fatigue loading and unloading was also recorded, which enabled investigation of the material degradation such as elastic modulus in various portions of fatigue life. Figure 4 and 5 shows the damaged specimens with negative and positive Poisson’s ratios following static and dynamic testing respectively. The final damage types are almost similar for both static and fatigue specimens. The damage starts with matrix cracking and longitudinal cracks along 10° and 70° layers, followed by major delamination and fibre breakage.

FIGURE 5 Final failure of hybrid specimens under fatigue loading

TABLE 3 Specimens fatigue life cycles

Laminate Type	Stacking Sequence	Damage Initiation Fatigue Life		Fatigue Final Life	
		Exp 01	Exp 02	Exp 01	Exp 02
Negative Poisson’s Ratio	[10 _c /80 _c /10 _g /70 _c] _s	36900	30350	89776	79364
Positive Poisson’s Ratio	[10 _c /45 _c /-45 _g /90 _c] _s	7605	4202	34127	27954

As mentioned above, the history of loading and displacement for each fatigue test was extracted up to the failure point of specimens. Using these data, it is possible to obtain the cyclic stress-strain diagram (hysteresis loop) related to the fatigue behaviour of each specimen. These diagrams for four different stages of laminates life are shown in Figures 6 and 7. These figures also show that the slope of the stress-strain of hysteresis loops (elastic modulus – E_{11}) are significantly decreased by increasing the fatigue loading cycles, indicating the progress of fatigue damage and consequently material degradation.

FIGURE 6 Hysteresis loops of positive Poisson's ratio laminate at first cycle, 25%,50%,75% and 98% of fatigue life

FIGURE 7 Hysteresis loops of negative Poisson's ratio laminate at first cycle 25%,50%,75% and 98% of fatigue life

RESULTS DISCUSSION

As Figure 3 shows, the stress-strain behaviours of both laminates with positive and negative Poisson's ratios have almost the same axial elastic modulus in the linear part of the curves. It is clear that the ultimate tensile stress for the laminate with positive Poisson's ratio (190 MPa) is larger than that with negative Poisson's ratio (136 MPa). Also, significant damage initiation stress (initiation of nonlinearity at stress-strain curves) for specimen with positive Poisson's ratio (165 MPa) is larger than that for negative Poisson's ratio (115 MPa). However, failure strain of the laminate with negative Poisson's ratio (1.13%) is larger than that with positive Poisson's ratio (0.93%). It is also worth to note that damage and failure behaviour of laminate with negative Poisson's ratio is more similar to pseudo ductile composite materials.

Applying a fatigue loading with the maximum stress of 75% of the damage initiation stress for each laminate showed that the specimens with negative Poisson's ratio can endure 89776 and 79364 loading cycles until final failure. However, the final failure fatigue lives for specimens with positive Poisson's ratio are significantly smaller (34127 and 27954 cycles). It indicates that the fatigue life of the laminates with negative Poisson's ratio can be about 60% larger than the fatigue life of laminates with positive Poisson's ratio.

Experimental observations also showed that when fatigue loading is applied, damage initiation occurs in laminates with a positive Poisson's ratio earlier than those with positive Poisson's ratio. To discuss the degradation of axial elastic modulus and progress of damage, information in Figures 6 and 7 have been quantified and presented in Table 4. This table shows that the degradation of axial elastic modulus in specimens with positive Poisson's ratio is much faster than that with negative Poisson's ratio.

The damage types and the sequence of their occurrence up to final failure are almost the same for both static and fatigue tests. The sequence of damage, as observed in fatigue testing can be explained as follows. At first, for both laminates, the matrix of the inner plates failed with a loud noise and evidence of delamination. After enduring loading cycles (about 33% total fatigue life of laminates), tiny oblique cracks developed on the outer surface of the laminates, resulting in matrix failure in the outer planes. Then by utilising the results obtained from a digital camera, visual observations, and analysing the emitted sounds during experimental testing, significant delamination observed between the layers and finally some fibres breakages were also observed in laminates with negative Poisson's ratio.

After examining the broken specimens, it was also observed that the laminates with negative Poisson's ratio suffered from glass fibre failure during the endurance of the fatigue cycles. As a result, at regions close to the contact point of the grips, carbon fibres have also experienced fractures. However, failure of reinforcing fibres did not occur in the specimens with a positive Poisson's ratio.

TABLE 4 E_{11} values and their degradation at different portions of the fatigue life for laminates

Cycles Done	Negative Poisson's Ratio		Positive Poisson's Ratio	
	E_{11} (GPa)	Axial Elastic Modulus Degradation (%)	E_{11} (GPa)	Axial Elastic Modulus Degradation (%)
First Cycle	27.50	0.0	27.78	0.0
25% Total Life	26.67	3.02	26.09	6.08
50% Total Life	25.45	7.45	24.29	12.56
75% Total Life	23.33	15.16	22.5	19.01
98% Total Life	17.5	36.36	17.14	38.30

CONCLUSION

Under static loading, the laminates with positive Poisson's ratio exhibit a larger ultimate tensile stress, but they also experience brittle failure. On the other hand, laminates with negative Poisson's ratio exhibit lower ultimate tensile stress, but behave like pseudo-ductile composites.

When applying a fatigue load of 75% of the damage initiation stress value corresponding to each laminate with a stress ratio of 0.1, the laminates with negative Poisson's ratio can withstand a higher number of cycles. Damage initiation starts earlier in laminates with positive Poisson's ratio and around the tolerance of 25% of the final life. Meanwhile, evidence of the onset of damage is observed in laminates with a negative Poisson's ratio after enduring about 50% of their final life, and the process of axial elastic modulus degradation in these laminates takes place at a lower speed.

Both laminates experience matrix cracking in the inner surfaces, which leads to delamination. Subsequently, as the minor cracks expand, the matrix of the outer plates also breaks down, ultimately resulting in specimen failure. Additionally, fibre breakage has been observed in the broken samples which have a negative Poisson's ratio.

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